

BIRDkiss

Formulation, implementation and usage of a DEBkiss model applied to birds

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This document is a technical report on the development of a new modelling framework, the BIRDkiss (Bird Ingestion and Reproduction Dynamic Energy Budget – keep it simple and suitable version). The work presented in this document is part of the TKplate 2.0 project, contract number OC/EFSA/SCER/2021/07 granted by EFSA to Utrecht University and partners. This project aims to refine and expand physiologically-based (PB) models and New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for use in risk assessment of chemicals.

The BIRDkiss is inspired from the DEBkiss modelling approach as proposed by Tjalling Jager and colleagues [3, 1, 2]. This modelling framework has been demonstrated to deliver similar results compared to the standard DEB model with primary parameters, both in the calibration and in the following prediction step [4].

The DEBkiss model is a simplification of the DEB model, the main modification being the suppression of the reserve compartment before the energy flux is split with a constant value of κ . Furthermore, in DEBkiss, the default 'currency' is not energy but mass as dry weight. Energy could be used instead, but it would have an impact on the value of the parameters related to transformations (assimilation of food for example).

The new modelling framework developed in this document, BIRDkiss, is an application of the DEBkiss model to the specific case of avian reproduction tests, as described in the OECD guideline as test No. 206.

As a reminder, the avian reproduction test is a test during which adult birds, often ducks or quails, are exposed to a compound in their food at a fixed concentration. After some time, reproduction is induced through light exposure patterns and various endpoints related to reproduction are measured, including the number of eggs laid. Furthermore, the individual weights and average daily food intake (approximately one measurement per week) of the adults are also measured.

The BIRDkiss model is intended to be fitted to data from avian reproduction tests using bayesian inference. It should require minimum extra inputs from the user beside the actual data from the test and produce plausible results in a reasonable amount of time. Ultimately, the fitted parameters of the model could be used to predict reproduction outputs under novel exposure profiles.

This document first describes the existing DEBkiss modelling framework. It then explores the limitations and opportunities offered by the unique application scenario of avian reproduction tests, before presenting the full BIRDkiss model that was developed in consequence. Finally, we describe the discrete version of the BIRDkiss model that was developed to mitigate the shortcomings of the original BIRDkiss model.

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1 The DEBkiss model

In this section we present the DEBkiss model such as we used it for the base of the BIRDkiss model. The DEBkiss modelling framework can be greatly extended with various modules in order to adapt to various scenarios, as explained in details in [2]. We chose to describe a pretty standard version of the DEBkiss model, only adding the maturity maintenance module as advised by Jager [2]

1.1 Schematic diagram of the mass fluxes

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the flows in the model. Nodes b and p denote switches at birth (start of feeding) and puberty (start of reproductive investment), as inspired from [2]

In Figure 1 is a representation of the mass fluxes modeled in the DEBkiss model. The assimilation flux J_A is divided following the fraction κ into two branches: growth and reproduction. A portion of these two branches is used for somatic and maturity maintenance, respectively. Mass transfers are adjusted by yield coefficients (y_{**}).

This diagram encompasses the three lifestages of the modelled organism: embryo, juvenile and adult. When transitioning from one stage to another, the fluxes are modified according to the switches represented as grey circles. Before hatching/birth, the assimilation flux is sourced at a constant rate from the buffer of the egg. After the hatching event, the assimilation flux is instead sourced from feeding (J_X). Hatching happens when the egg buffer W_b reaches 0. Before sexual maturity is reached, the reproduction branch goes toward an increase in maturity, a hidden variable of the model (as in, not numerically tracked). After puberty, the branch goes toward a reproduction buffer W_R that is eventually used to produce eggs. Since maturity is a hidden variable, puberty is determined by the time when the organism reaches a given volume or mass.

1.2 List of variables and parameters

Symbol	Dimension	Definition	Equation
f	-	Scaled functional response (0-1)	Equation 1.2
J_A	m_a/t	Mass flux for assimilation	Equation 1.4
J_H	m_a/t	Mass flux for maturation	
J_J	m_a/t	Mass flux for maturity maintenance	Equation 1.11
J_M	m_a/t	Mass flux for maintenance	Equation 1.9
J_R	m_a/t	Mass flux for reproduction	Equation 1.10
J_V	m/t	Mass flux for structure	Equation 1.9
J_X	m_f/t	Mass flux of food	Equation 1.1
L	l	Structural length	Equation 1.1
ΔR	$\#$	Number of eggs in a clutch	Equation 1.12
W_B	m_a	Mass of assimilates buffer in egg	Equation 1.5
W_R	m_a	Mass of reproduction buffer in adult	Equations 1.7 and 1.13
W_V	m	Mass of structural body	Equation 1.6
W_W	m	Total body weight	See section 1.3.3

Table 1: List of the variables of the DEBkiss model

Symbol	Dimension	Definition
d_v	m/l^3	Dry-weight density of structure
F_m^a	$l_e^3/(l^2t)$	Maximum area-specific search rate
J_{Am}^a	$m_a/(l^2t)$	Maximum area-specific assimilation rate
J_J^v	$m_a/(l^3t)$	Maturity maintenance costs
J_M^v	$m_a/(l^3t)$	Volume-specific maintenance costs
W_{B0}	m_a	Assimilates in a single freshly laid egg
W_{Vp}	m	Structural body mass at puberty
X	m_f/l_e^3	Food density in the environment
y_{AV}	m_a/m	Yield of assimilates on structure (starvation)
y_{AX}	m_a/m_f	Yield of assimilates on food
y_{BA}	m_a/m_a	Yield of egg buffer on assimilates
y_{VA}	m/m_a	Yield of structure on assimilates (growth)
κ	-	Fraction of assimilation flux for the soma

Table 2: List of primary parameters of the DEBkiss model, with dimensions given in mass (m for body, m_a for assimilates, and m_f for food. Usually in dry weight), length (l_e for environment, l for organism), numbers ($\#$), time (t).

In Table 2 are described the primary parameters of the DEBkiss model. A primary parameter is a parameter that is directly linked to a metabolic process and that does not depend on other parameters. We can also mention compound parameters, which are combinations of primary parameters that may be easier for the user to provide values for. They can be used to deduce values for primary parameters (see, for example, chapter 3 of [2]). Examples of compound parameters are the maximal

volumetric length L_m and the von Bertalanffy growth rate constant r_B .

$$L_m = \kappa \frac{J_{Am}^a}{J_M^v} \quad \text{and} \quad r_B = \frac{y_{VA}}{3d_v} J_M^v$$

1.3 Model formulation

1.3.1 Feeding

The equation for the feeding mass flux is the following:

$$J_X = f(t) \cdot J_{Xm}^a \cdot L(t)^2 \quad \text{with} \quad L(t)^3 = \frac{W_V}{d_v} \quad (1.1)$$

The scaled functional response f can be used as a primary parameter, or it can be computed using the following forcing function of the food density X .

$$f = \frac{X}{X + X_\kappa} \quad \text{with} \quad X_\kappa = \frac{J_{Xm}^a}{F_m^a} \quad (1.2)$$

The maximum area-specific feeding rate J_{Xm}^a can be computed like so:

$$J_{Xm}^a = \frac{J_{Am}^a}{y_{AX}} \quad (1.3)$$

1.3.2 Assimilation

The assimilation flux is different before birth (embryo stage) and after birth. In the latter case, the flux corresponds to a fraction of the mass of ingested food.

$$\begin{aligned} J_A &= J_{Am}^a \cdot L(t)^2 & \text{if } W_B > 0 \\ &= J_X \cdot y_{AX} & \text{if } W_B = 0 \text{ (after birth)} \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

1.3.3 Buffers

As explained in section 1.1, there are three buffers in the DEBkiss model: egg reserve before hatching, structure and reproduction buffer. Below are the equations that manage the dynamic of these buffers. Here, the time 0 corresponds to the start of the embryonic phase.

$$\frac{d}{dt} W_B = -J_A \quad \text{until } W_B = 0, \text{ with } W_B(0) = W_{B0} \quad (1.5)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} W_V = J_V \quad \text{with } W_V(0) \approx 0 \quad (1.6)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} W_R = J_R \quad \text{with } W_R(0) = 0 \quad (1.7)$$

Note that the total weight of the egg (before birth) or individual (after birth) is the sum of the structural body mass (W_V) and whatever other buffer is available (W_B or W_R or nothing). Hence, the dry weight of an immature individual is equal to its structural body mass. In other words, the total weight can be written as follows:

$$W_w = \begin{cases} W_V + W_B & \text{if } W_B > 0 \\ W_V & \text{if } W_B = 0 \text{ and } W_V < W_{Vp} \\ W_V + W_R & \text{if } W_V \geq W_{Vp} \end{cases} \quad (1.8)$$

1.3.4 Growth

The growth is equal to the mass allocated to soma minus the mass used for the structure maintenance.

$$J_V = y_{VA}(\kappa \cdot J_A - J_M) \quad \text{with } J_M = J_M^v \cdot L(t)^3 \quad (1.9)$$

1.3.5 Reproduction

Reproduction starts once maturity has been reached. The mass allocated to the reproduction buffer is equal to the $(1 - \kappa)$ fraction of the assimilation flow minus the mass required for maturity maintenance. Before puberty is reached ($W_V < W_{Vp}$), the quantity $(1 - \kappa)J_A - J_J$ is “burnt” in order to mature.

$$\begin{aligned} J_R &= (1 - \kappa)J_A - J_J && \text{if } W_V \geq W_{Vp} \\ &= 0 && \text{if } W_V < W_{Vp} \end{aligned} \quad (1.10)$$

Because maturity is a hidden variable of this model, the maturity maintenance costs are computed based on the structural length. Since the maturity does not increase after puberty is reached, we use the length at puberty L_p to compute the maturity maintenance costs of an adult.

$$\begin{aligned} J_J &= J_J^v \cdot L^3 && \text{when } W_V < W_{Vp} \\ &= J_J^v \cdot L_p^3 && \text{when } W_V \geq W_{Vp} \text{ (note: } L_p^3 = W_{Vp}/d_V) \end{aligned} \quad (1.11)$$

The trigger for egg production can vary depending on the species. For example, the egg event can happen when $W_R \geq W_{B0}/y_{BA}$, or after a given time interval. In any case, the event is described with the following equations:

$$\Delta R = \text{floor} \left(\frac{y_{BA} \cdot W_R}{W_{B0}} \right) \quad (1.12)$$

$$W_R = W_R - \frac{\Delta R \cdot W_{B0}}{y_{BA}} \quad (1.13)$$

1.4 Special case: starvation

Starvation occurs when the mass flow allocated to soma is smaller than the mass flow required for somatic maintenance ($\kappa J_A < J_M$). It can be broken down in the three following cases.

Case 1: $J_A > J_M + J_J$ or $W_R > 0$

In this case, the overall assimilation flow is sufficient to ensure somatic and maturity maintenance, or there is mass to be retrieved from the reproduction buffer. Since the mass flow allocated to soma is not enough for maintenance alone, growth is halted. Furthermore, only the leftover mass after somatic and maturation maintenance goes to the reproduction buffer. The J_R rate can even be negative, which corresponds to the case where mass is retrieved from the reproduction buffer to

compensate maintenance.

$$J_V = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$J_R = J_A - (J_M + J_J) \quad (1.15)$$

Case 2: $J_M + J_J \geq J_A > J_M$ and $W_R = 0$

In this case, there is not enough overall mass to ensure both somatic and maturity maintenance, but there is enough for just somatic maintenance. Hence, growth and reproduction are halted, but there is no shrinkage. The leftover energy after somatic maintenance is used for maturity maintenance, with the hypothesis that this lack of mass does not have any consequence.

$$J_V = J_R = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$J_J = J_A - J_M \quad (1.17)$$

Case 3: $J_A \leq J_M$ and $W_R = 0$

In this case, the overall assimilation flow is not sufficient to ensure somatic maintenance, and no mass can be retrieved from the reproduction buffer to compensate. Instead, the structure will be used, leading to a reduction in size. Reproduction is halted. Once again, we make the hypothesis that the lack of mass flow toward maturity maintenance does not have any consequence.

$$J_R = J_J = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

$$J_V = \frac{(J_A - J_M)}{y_{AV}} \quad (1.19)$$

This starvation mechanism is but a proposition from [2]. Behaviour under food stress can vary between species. Also, special care must be taken when shrinkage occurs for a prolonged period, as well as the possible positive feedback loop between starvation caused by damage dynamic and increase of the toxic compound concentration when shrinkage occurs.

1.5 Simplified DEBkiss

With additional assumptions, it is possible to solve the growth ODE and to obtain a simple set of two equations with only 6 model parameters.

$$L(t) = f.L_m - (f.L_m - L_0).e^{-r_B.t} \quad (1.20)$$

$$R_c(t) = f.R_m \cdot \frac{L^2(t)}{L_m^2} \quad \text{when } L(t) > L_p \quad (1.21)$$

r_B (growth rate constant), L_m (maximum volumetric length) and R_m (maximum reproduction rate) are compound parameters linked to the underlying DEBkiss primary parameters. See equations 2.19 and 2.20 in [2]. Variable $R_c(t)$ stands for cumulative reproduction. Parameter L_0 is length at time 0.

This simplification comes at the cost of several limitations that are described in section 2.1 where we explain why the simplified DEBkiss is not very suitable for our application scenario.

1.6 Damage dynamic

In this section, we describe the way the DEBkiss model can be used in ecotoxicology to predict the effect of toxicant in organisms. It is described in details in the Chapter 5 of [2]. First, we describe how the amount of “damage” can be predicted. Then, we explain how this “damage” can affect the parameters of the model via the notion of stress.

1.6.1 Variables and parameters introduced by damage dynamic

Symbol	Dimension	Type	Definition
b_b^w	l_e^3/m_q	Parameter	Effect strength (sub-lethal) referenced to the external concentration
C	m_q/l_e^3	Variable	Concentration of toxicant in the contamination medium
D	m_q/l_e^3	Variable	Scaled damage level referenced to the external concentration
k_d	$1/t$	Parameter	Dominant rate constant
K_{RV}	m/m_a	Parameter	Partition coefficient reproduction buffer-structure
s	-	Variable	Stress level on a metabolic process
z_b^w	m_q/l_e^3	Parameter	Effect threshold (sub-lethal) referenced to the external concentration

Table 3: List of DEBkiss parameters and variables related to damage dynamics, with dimensions given in mass (m for body, m_a for assimilates, and m_q for chemical), length (l_e for environment), time (t).

1.6.2 Scaled damage

When no internal concentration profile is available from experimental data, the scaled damage referenced to the external concentration (D) is used. The base equation for this variable is the following:

$$\frac{d}{dt}D = k_d(C - D) \quad (1.22)$$

With this scaled damage, we do not know if the effect is driven by the toxicokinetics (damages repair quickly relatively to the variation rate of the internal concentration) or by the damage dynamics (compound accumulates and is eliminated quickly, but the associated damages are slow to repair). Hence k_d is called a dominant rate constant and is not necessarily equivalent to an elimination rate constant k_e .

Feedback processes are mechanisms where life-history traits affect the damage dynamic. There are three types of feedback that are considered in [2]: changes in the surface/volume ratio of the organism (affecting both uptake and elimination), growth dilution and elimination with reproduction. It’s worth to note that while these processes make sense in the context of a TK driven scaled damage, it is not necessarily the case when considering a damage dynamic driven scaled damage. For example, what exactly represents the damage level in the body of a bird? And while it makes sense that passing a given quantity of a compound to an egg would reduce the overall quantity in

the body, can it apply to a level of damage? And would a different surface/volume ratio lead to a slower (or faster) damage repair (“elimination”) rate?

This is why a generic equation of scaled damage with the possibility to include or not all or part of the four mechanisms mentioned above was proposed in [1]:

$$\frac{d}{dt}D^w = k_d(x_u C_w - x_e D^w) - (x_G + x_R)D^w \quad (1.23)$$

With the definition of the x_* factors being:

$$[x_u, x_e, x_G, x_R] = \mathbf{X} \circ \left[\frac{L_m}{L(t)}, \frac{L_m}{L(t)}, \frac{1}{W_V} \frac{d}{dt} W_V, R \frac{W_{B0}}{W_V} K_{RV} \right] \quad (1.24)$$

$$\text{if } \mathbf{X}(1) = 0 \text{ then } x_u = 1 \quad \text{if } \mathbf{X}(2) = 0 \text{ then } x_e = 1 \quad (1.25)$$

With K_{RV} the partition coefficient of the compound between the reproduction buffer and the structure (in m/m_a).

\mathbf{X} is a switch, a vector of zeros and ones. Its values can be set to include or not the corresponding feedback mechanisms.

It is noted in [1] that in standard toxicity test (reproduction over time under constant exposure), there is not enough information to pinpoint which of these mechanisms should be considered and that, by extension, the decision has little impact on the model fit. However, it could have a considerable impact when using the results of this fit in extrapolation simulations with, for example, time-varying exposure.

1.6.3 Stress level

Once the damage is known, it needs to be linked to a stress level s that will be used to linearly change one or more DEBKiss parameters, once a certain threshold is reached.

$$s = b_b^w \max(0, D^w - z_b^w) \quad (1.26)$$

The index b stands for “sub-lethal”. In the case of a lethal effect, the index s for “survival” would be used instead. z_b^w is not directly equivalent to the “No effect concentration” due to the feedback mechanisms interfering in the evolution of the scaled damage.

To link this stress level to a primary parameter (p) in a linear fashion, most often one of these transformations will be applied:

$$p \longrightarrow p(1 + s) \quad \text{or} \quad p \longrightarrow p \max(0, 1 - s) \quad \text{or} \quad p \longrightarrow p/(1 + s) \quad (1.27)$$

To make the model application more flexible depending on the physiological mode of action (pMoA) of the toxicant, one can separate the stress level based on the affected process (assimilation or feeding, maintenance costs, growth costs, reproduction costs¹) using the following equation:

$$[s_A, s_M, s_G, s_R] = s \times \mathbf{S} \quad \text{with } s_A \longrightarrow \min(1, s_A) \quad (1.28)$$

Just like with \mathbf{X} , the vector \mathbf{S} is a switch that can be used to easily select the stress effects to

¹The pMoA “hazard on reproduction” is ignored here because of its similitude with the costs for reproduction. See [1].

include. See table 6.1 of [2] for a proposal of a set of stress functions, and see table 5.3 for a more extensive list of possibly affected primary parameters. As an example, the effect on reproduction costs is applied to the y_{BA} parameter with the following equation:

$$y_{BA} \longrightarrow \frac{y_{BA}}{1 + s_R} \quad (1.29)$$

The pMoA is a combination of one or more stressor effects.

2 Elements for our application of the DEBkiss

As a reminder, we aim at creating a model based on the DEBkiss that would be applied specifically in the context of avian reproduction tests. These studies provide the following data:

- Average daily feed consumption (usually one measure every week or every two weeks);
- Individual weights (usually measured a few times over the course of the study);
- Number of eggs laid per female;
- Various counts based on the status of the laid eggs (cracked, defective, fertile...);
- Various counts and measures on the hatchlings resulting from the eggs produced during the test.

With a DEB-based model, we want to take as input the feed consumption and to predict the resulting weight variations and egg production. After fitting the model to the data provided by the reproduction test, we could then use it to predict the number of eggs laid, our primary variable of interest, under different, possibly variable exposure scenarios. In this section, we summarise our thought process for modifying the DEBkiss model and elaborate the new BIRDkiss model.

2.1 The simplified DEBkiss case

Firstly, we will explain why the simplified DEBkiss is not a good fit for our purpose as mentioned in section 1.5:

- The simplified DEBkiss is exempt of reproduction buffer. It means that the energy allocated to reproduction is directly converted to egg and that, in a sense, the production of offspring is continuous over time. Furthermore, it means the reproduction buffer cannot be used in strategies against starvation, a frequent case when inducing stress in adult, non-growing individuals.
- Solving the ODE equation to reach the simplified DEBkiss form requires all of the parameters to be constant, including f . This is not compatible with the data we want to use that includes varying feed consumption over time. This issue could possibly be solved by using the differential equations of the simplified DEBkiss:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dL}{dt} = r_B (f \cdot L_m - L) \\ \frac{dR_c}{dt} = \frac{R_m}{L_m^3 - L_p^3} (f \cdot L_M \cdot L^2(t) - L_p^3) \quad \text{if } L(t) > L_p \end{cases}$$

- In the simplified DEBkiss, the metabolic processes (assimilation, etc.) are not clearly separated but rather summarised together. It makes it harder to implement stress effect on specific metabolic processes based of pMoA.
- Due to the use of compound parameters, there is a risk that the selected parameter values may lead to impossible underlying DEBkiss primary parameters (for example, yield coefficients y_{**} greater than 1).
- Finally, the simplified DEBkiss does not include maturity maintenance, which is against the recommendations from [2].

2.2 Initial state of the simulation

The DEBkiss model is capable of modelling all the lifestages of an organism. However, in the case of reproduction tests, we lack information on the juvenile stage of the studied birds. Furthermore, the rearing of the birds before the start of the test is expected to be standardised and devoid of particular events. Thus, it seems unnecessary to model the studied birds before the start of the reproduction test. This was not an option when considering the full DEB model due to the numerous buffers for which the state at the start of the test could not be determined, but the DEBkiss model only contains 3 buffers, plus the egg count which obviously starts at zero.

We can say that the egg buffer $W_B = 0$ since we are dealing with adults and not embryos. For the reproduction buffer, we state that $W_R = 0$ at the start of the test. This corresponds to the hypothesis that the birds just reached maturity at the start of the experiment. It seems to be not so far from reality as the birds studied in the tests are usually very young and only nearing their first reproduction period. With these two buffers empty, the structure weight at the start of the test is equal to the entire weight of the animals ($W_V = W_W$). We thus have the initial state of the buffers in the model:

$$\begin{cases} W_B(0) = 0 \\ W_R(0) = 0 \\ W_V(0) = W_W(0) \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

2.3 Exploiting feeding data

The biggest different between the DEBkiss that we described in the first part of this document and the model that we are creating is the amount of information available regarding food. Since we have records of the amount of food ingested by each bird, we do not need to use the formulas for J_X (equation 1.1) and f (equation 1.2) which rely on searching and assimilation rates. Instead, we can use a much simpler formula where J_X , a mass flux, is set to the daily food intake of the modelled organism.

Following this decision, we also choose to remove the length and volume elements of our model, only working with weights. Indeed, the length is primarily used to determine the feeding flux in the DEBkiss model. With the length of the organism no longer used, we also remove the density of structure parameter d_v and modify the maintenance costs rates J_J^v and J_M^v to depend on weight and not on volume.

One thing that is specific to avian reproduction is that the amount of feed ingested per individual notably increases during egg laying periods. This increase should mostly benefits the reproduction functions, which would not be the case if the distribution of mass between the two branches of the κ junction was kept identical before and after the reproduction induction. The somatic functions would proportionally receive the same increase in mass flow as the reproduction functions. To solve this issue, we propose to apply two different κ fractions based on whether or not reproduction is occurring.

2.4 Avian egg production

Due to the structure of the avian reproduction tests, where mature adults have a phase during which they do not reproduce, we have the following questions to answer:

- When does the reproduction W_R start filling? At the start of the test (when maturity is reached) or when the reproduction is induced via light patterns?
- What is the condition to trigger the production of an egg? When enough mass is present in the reproduction buffer? If this buffer starts filling from the start of the test, then can multiple eggs be laid at the same time the moment reproduction is induced?

We chose to have the reproduction buffer starts filling up from the start of the test rather than from the moment reproduction is induced. This was to emulate the fact that non reproducing birds fed *ad libitum* would be building reserve for the next reproduction period.

To avoid the risk of multiple eggs being laid at the start of the reproduction period in the eventuality that the reproduction buffer would have filled up considerably during the first phase of the test, we chose to add a restriction to the egg production: a maximum of one egg can be laid every X hours, and only if there is enough mass in the reproduction buffer. If for example the quantity X is set to 24 hours, this rule could emulate the fact that birds tend to lay their eggs at a given time of day.

3 The BIRDkiss model

In this section we present the BIRDkiss model that we elaborated based on the knowledge from the two previous sections. In addition to the deterministic part of the model, we also present the stochastic laws applied to the model outputs. Furthermore, the model being intended to be used in the context of Bayesian inference, we also present the priors applied to relevant parameters. Finally, we discuss the limitations that were found during the implementation of this initial BIRDkiss model and the choice to move towards .

3.1 Schematic diagram of the mass fluxes

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the mass flows in the BIRDkiss model.

Figure 2 is a representation of the mass fluxes modelled in the BIRDkiss model. It is a κ fraction model similar to the DEBkiss model. Contrary to its inspiration, it is only applicable to the adult lifestage. Furthermore, the top part of the diagram was modified in order to accommodate the feeding data available in our setting.

3.2 List of variables, parameters, priors and user data

Symbol	Dimension	Support	Definition
J_A	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass flux for assimilation
J_J	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass flux for maturity maintenance
J_M	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Mass flux for somatic maintenance
J_R	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}	Mass flux for reproduction
J_V	m/t	\mathbb{R}	Mass flux for structure
N_{egg}	#	\mathbb{N}	Number of eggs laid since time 0
W_R	m_a	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass of reproduction buffer
W_V	m	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Mass of structural body
W_W	m	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Total body weight

Table 4: List of the variables of the BIRDkiss model

Symbol	Dimension	Support	Definition	Prior
β_R	1/#	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Rate of the gamma distribution governing egg counts	$\text{Uniform}(-3, 3)$ on log 10
J_J^w	m_a/m_a	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass maturity maintenance costs	$\text{Uniform}(-5, 2)$ on log 10
J_M^w	m_a/m_a	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass somatic maintenance costs	$\text{Uniform}(-5, 2)$ on log 10
σ_W	m	\mathbb{R}	Standard deviation of the normal distribution governing weights	$\text{Uniform}(0, 1000)$
W_{B0}	m_a	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Assimilates in a single freshly-laid egg	Given by user
W_{Vp}	m	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Structural body mass at puberty	Given by user
y_{AV}	m_a/m	$[0, 1]$	Yield of assimilates on structure (starvation)	$\beta(0.5, 0.5)$
y_{AX}	m_a/m_f	$[0, 1]$	Yield of assimilates on food	$\beta(0.5, 0.5)$
y_{BA}	m_a/m_a	$[0, 1]$	Yield of egg buffer on assimilates	$\beta(0.5, 0.5)$
y_{VA}	m/m_a	$[0, 1]$	Yield of structure on assimilates (growth)	$\beta(0.5, 0.5)$
κ_1	-	$[0, 1]$	Split assimilation flux for soma outside of reproduction	$\beta(0.5, 0.5)$
κ_2	-	$[0, 1]$	Split assimilation flux for soma during reproduction	$\beta(0.5, 0.5)$
T_{egg}	t	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Minimum time between two laying events	Given by user
t_s	t	\mathbb{R}^+	Time at which reproduction is induced	Given by user
W_{w0}	m_a	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Body weight at time 0	Given by user

Table 5: List of primary parameters of the BIRDkiss model, with dimensions given in mass (m for body, m_a for assimilates, and m_f for food), numbers (#) and time (t).

Name	Unit	Definition
R array	#	Cumulative egg count data: for each described time, the number of eggs laid since time 0.
W array	g	Weight data: for each described time, the weight of the bird at that time.
X array	g/d	Feed ingestion data: for each described time, the average daily feed intake since the last measurement.

Table 6: List of data points from the avian reproduction tests used by the BIRDkiss model

We chose to use wet weights instead of dry weights in order to simplify the use of the avian reproduction tests data.

3.3 Model formulation

3.3.1 Assimilation

The assimilation is based on an estimation of the feeding rate at the time of interest made by linear interpolation on the feeding data provided by the user.

$$J_A = \text{linear_interpolation}(\text{X array})(t) \times y_{AX} \quad (3.1)$$

The assimilation flux is then split following a κ fraction that varies depending on time:

$$\kappa = \begin{cases} \kappa_1 & \text{if } t \leq t_s \\ \kappa_2 & \text{if } t > t_s \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

3.3.2 Buffers

The BIRDkiss model contains only two of the three buffers of the DEBkiss model: W_V and W_R . Their dynamic is the same as in the source model. However in this case, the time 0 represents the start of the avian reproduction test.

$$\frac{d}{dt}W_V(t) = J_V(t) \text{ with } W_V(0) = W_{w0} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}W_R(t) = J_R(t) \text{ with } W_R(0) = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

The total weight W_w is the sum of the two buffers:

$$W_W(t) = W_V(t) + W_R(t) \quad (3.5)$$

The observed weights are linked to the predicted total weight with the following distribution:

$$W_{obs}(t) \sim \text{Normal}(W_w(t), \sigma_W) \quad (3.6)$$

3.3.3 Growth

The growth is unchanged from the DEBkiss model. The computation of the structure maintenance costs is slightly altered due to using weights instead of lengths.

$$J_V(t) = y_{VA}(\kappa \cdot J_A(t) - J_M(t)) \quad \text{with } J_M(t) = J_M^w \cdot W_V(t) \quad (3.7)$$

3.3.4 Reproduction

Although the actual production of eggs can only start once $t > t_s$ (reproduction is induced via light patterns), the reproduction buffer fills up from the start.

$$J_R(t) = (1 - \kappa)J_A(t) - J_J \quad \text{with } J_J = J_J^w \cdot W_{Vp} \quad (3.8)$$

The conditions for egg laying are the following: time must be after t_s and match the minimum time interval between two laying events: $t = t_s + i \times T_{egg}$ with i and integer. Additionally, the mass in the reproduction buffer must be sufficient to produce an egg: $W_R(t) \geq W_{B0}/y_{BA}$.

Once the conditions are met for an egg event, it can be described with the following equations:

$$N_{egg} = N_{egg} + 1 \tag{3.9}$$

$$W_R(t) = W_R(t) - \frac{W_{B0}}{y_{BA}} \tag{3.10}$$

The observed egg counts are linked to the predicted egg count with the following distribution:

$$N_{egg.obs}(t) \sim \text{Gamma}(N_{egg}(t) \times \beta_R, \beta_R) \tag{3.11}$$

3.4 Special case: starvation

The BIRDkiss model has the same rules than the DEBkiss model concerning starvation situations. Please refer to section 1.4 for detailed explanations.

3.5 Damage dynamics

The damage dynamics of the BIRDkiss model as described above has not been fleshed out, as the decision to switch to a discrete model was made before its implementation. See the discrete BIRDkiss formulation (section 4.3) for its toxicity part.

3.6 Implementation challenges

The BIRDkiss model as described above has been implemented in R and stan. Throughout its development, it was tested on a simulated dataset as well as two datasets extracted from EFSA dossiers (Bobwhite - Deltamethrin and Bobwhite - Clomazone). One major issue that arose was the duration of the fitting process. Despite parallelisation of the computations, the inference process with a standard number of chains and iterations took several days on real datasets. This was especially concerning as so far only one fourth of the full dataset was used on average, namely the data from the control replicates that were not exposed to the studied substance as the toxicology part of the model was not implemented. The fitting process with the full datasets could only be much longer, which was unacceptable for a model developed for routine use.

Hence it was decided that the model would be discretised to avoid the lengthy steps of solving differential equations during the inference process. In addition, some additional changes were made to the model during the discretisation process. The discrete BIRDkiss model is fully described in the next section and a summary of the changes made is available at the top of section 4.3.

4 The discrete BIRDkiss model

In this section we present the model that was obtained from discretising the BIRDkiss model. As it is to be used in the context of Bayesian inference, we present in addition to the deterministic part of the model the stochastic laws applied to the model outputs as well as the priors applied to relevant parameters.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the mass flows in the discrete BIRDkiss model.

4.1 Schematic diagram of the mass fluxes

Figure 3 shows a representation of the mass flows in the discrete BIRDkiss model. It is very similar to the original BIRDkiss diagram, the key difference being the removal of the maturity maintenance cost.

4.2 List of variables, parameters, priors and user data

Symbol	Dimension	Support	Definition
D	m_q/m_f	\mathbb{R}^+	Scaled damage level referenced to food concentration
J_A	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass flux for assimilation
J_M	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Mass flux for somatic maintenance
J_V	m_a/t	\mathbb{R}	Mass flux for structure
N_{egg}	#	\mathbb{N}	Number of eggs laid since time 0
s	-	\mathbb{R}^+	Stress level
W_R	m_a	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass of reproduction buffer
W_V	m_a	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Mass of structural body
W_W	m_a	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Total body weight

Table 7: List of the variables of the discrete BIRDkiss model

Symbol	Dimension	Support	Definition	Prior
α_s	m_q/m_f	\mathbb{R}^+	Median of the log-logistic distribution of the toxicity threshold	$\mathbf{exp}(0.1)$
β_R	$1/\#$	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Rate of the gamma distribution governing egg counts	$\mathbf{inv.gamma}(1, 0.1)$
β_s	-	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Shape of the log-logistic distribution of the toxicity threshold	$\mathbf{inv.gamma}(1, 0.1)$
J_M^w	$m_a/m_a.t$	\mathbb{R}^+	Mass somatic maintenance costs	$\mathbf{exp}(0.1)$
k_d	$1/t$	\mathbb{R}^+	Dominant rate constant	$\mathbf{exp}(0.1)$
σ_W	m_a	\mathbb{R}	Standard deviation of the normal distribution governing weights	$\mathbf{Uniform}(0, 1000)$
W_{B0}	m_a	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Assimilates in a single freshly-laid egg	Given by user
y_{AX}	m_a/m_f	$[0, 1]$	Yield of assimilates on food	$\beta(0.8, 0.8)$
y_{BA}	m_a/m_a	$[0, 1]$	Yield of egg buffer on assimilates	$\beta(0.8, 0.8)$
y_{BU}	t/m_a	$[0, 1]$	Scale parameter	$\beta(0.8, 0.8)$
κ_1	-	$[0, 1]$	Split assimilation flux for soma outside of reproduction	$\beta(0.8, 0.8)$
κ_2	-	$[0, 1]$	Split assimilation flux for soma during reproduction	$\beta(0.8, 0.8)$
t_s	t	\mathbb{R}^+	Time at which reproduction is induced	Given by user
W_{w0}	m_a	\mathbb{R}^{+*}	Body weight at time 0	Given by user

Table 8: List of primary parameters of the discrete BIRDKiss model, with dimensions given in mass (m_a for assimilates, m_f for food), numbers (#) and time (t).

Name	Unit	Definition
C	ppm	Concentration of toxicant in food for each time point.
R array	#	Cumulative egg count data: for each described time, the number of eggs laid since time 0.
W array	g	Weight data: for each described time, the weight of the bird at that time.
X array	g/d	Feed ingestion data: for each described time, the average daily feed intake since the last measurement.

Table 9: List of data points from the avian reproduction tests used by the discrete BIRDKiss model

4.3 Model formulation

The BIRDKiss model was discretized over the time interval $T = t_2 - t_1$. In our implementation of the model, we set this time interval to one day. Just like the original BIRDKiss, the discrete model differentiates two kappa values, $kappa_p$ and $kappa$ (see equation 3.2).

In the following sections, the discrete BIRDKiss model is described. Before that, we present a list of all the differences between the original BIRDKiss and its discrete version:

- Removed the starvation mechanisms;

- Removed the maturity maintenance cost;
- Removed the conversion from assimilate to structure (y_{VA} factor);
- Added toxicity mechanisms;
- Added a carrying capacity to the reproduction buffer;
- Switched to continuous egg laying once t_s is reached.

4.3.1 Assimilation

The assimilation flux is identical to the one found in the original BIRDKiss:

$$J_A(T) = y_{AX} \times \text{linear_interpolation}(X \text{ array})(t_1) \quad (4.1)$$

4.3.2 Growth

The growth mechanism is similar to the one found in the original BIRDKiss, however the conversion factor y_{VA} (from assimilate to structure) was removed.

Discrete equation:

$$W_V(t_2) = \frac{\kappa \times J_A(T)}{J_M^w} - \left(\frac{\kappa \times J_A(T)}{J_M^w} - W_V(t_1) \right) e^{-J_M^w \times T} \quad (4.2)$$

Which corresponds to the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dW_V(t)}{dt} = \kappa J_A(t) - J_M^w W_V(t) \quad (4.3)$$

4.3.3 Reproduction

The reproduction part of the model was what changed the most with the discretisation. To reduce the use of “if” statements that made the inference less straight-forward, the rule on egg production “one egg every X hours” was removed. Hence, a new mechanism was required to avoid the production of multiple eggs at the start of the reproduction period. This would be a carrying capacity that caps the reproduction to a maximum weight of W_{B0}/y_{BA} . This translates to the conversion of the assimilation flux to the the reproduction buffer growing less and less efficient as the buffer approaches this quantity.

In addition, the maturity maintenance cost was removed.

Discrete equation:

$$W_R(t_2) = \frac{W_{B0}}{y_{BA}} - \left(\frac{W_{B0}}{y_{BA}} - W_R(t_1) \right) e^{-(1-\kappa)J_A(T) \times \frac{y_{BA}}{W_{B0}} \times T} \quad (4.4)$$

Which corresponds to the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dW_R(t)}{dt} = (1 - \kappa)J_A(t) \left(1 - \frac{y_{BA}W_R(t)}{W_{B0}} \right) \quad (4.5)$$

The removal of the “one egg every X hours” rule led to a form of continuous egg laying mechanism where, once $t_1 > t_s$, the reproduction buffer is fully emptied at each time step (corresponding to one day) as its content is converted into a number of eggs based on the weight of a single fresh egg. As one can expect, the number of egg produced each day is not necessarily discrete, it is simply larger or equal to zero.

Note that a stress variable was added to the number of eggs equation. The damage dynamics is detailed and explained in the next section.

$$N_{egg}(t_2) = N_{egg}(t_1) + \frac{(1 - \text{stress}(t_2)) \times W_R(t_2) \times y_{BA}}{W_{B0}} \quad (4.6)$$

$$W_R(t_2) = 0 \quad (4.7)$$

The consistent emptying of the reproduction buffer could be considered as a full removal of the reproduction buffer once the reproduction has started. However it is not the case before ($0 > t > t_s$) and that is why it was not removed from the model diagram. This is also why we still write:

$$W_W(t) = W_V(t) + W_R(t) \quad (4.8)$$

4.3.4 Damage dynamics

The damage dynamics of the discrete BIRDkiss were kept as their simplest in order to not further complexify the already lengthy inference process. The entering dose derives from the assimilation flux J_A , the concentration in the food and a conversion factor y_{BU} . To convert this dose into damage, we used the base equation of the scaled damage referenced to the external concentration (D) as described in section 1.6.2. We did not include any feedback process to this variable.

$$\text{dose}(t_1) = y_{BU} \times J_A(t_1) \times C(t_1) \quad (4.9)$$

$$D(t_2) = \text{dose}(t_1) + (D(t_1) - \text{dose}(t_1))e^{-k_d \times T} \quad (4.10)$$

The above discrete equation of the scaled damage corresponds to the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dD(t)}{dt} = (\text{dose}(t) - D(t))k_d \quad (4.11)$$

The stress that links the scaled damage to actual effects on the model’s parameters was written as a variable bound between 0 (when the damage tends towards 0) and 1 (when the damage tends towards infinity). This variable is then used in the egg production equation (see equation 4.6) to increase the egg production cost by reducing the conversion yield of reproduction buffer assimilate into egg matter (y_{BA}).

$$\text{stress}(t_2) = \frac{D(t_2)^{\beta_s}}{\alpha_s^{\beta_s} + \max(D(t_1), D(t_2))^{\beta_s}} \quad (4.12)$$

4.3.5 Stochastic part

The stochastic part allows to link the deterministic part of the model with the distribution of observations from the different replicates.

The observed weights are linked to the predicted total weight with the following distribution:

$$W_{obs}(t) \sim \text{Normal}(W_w(t), \sigma_W) \quad (4.13)$$

As for the observed egg counts, they are linked to the predicted egg count with the following distribution:

$$N_{egg.obs}(t) \sim \text{Gamma}(N_{egg}(t) \times \beta_R, \beta_R) \quad (4.14)$$

The gamma distribution was selected instead of a distribution with discrete values in order to accommodate for cases when the egg counts provided by the user are averages, possibly non integer values. This happens when eggs can only be counted for several females (for example, when multiple females are kept per pen).

References

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Annex

Integration process

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dD(t)}{dt} &= k_d \cdot (\text{dose} - D(t)) \\ \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{dD(t)}{\text{dose} - D(t)} &= \int_{t_1}^{t_2} k_d \cdot dt \\ [-\ln |\text{dose} - D(t)|]_{t_1}^{t_2} &= k_d \cdot (t_2 - t_1) \\ \ln(\text{dose} - D(t_1)) - \ln(\text{dose} - D(t_2)) &= k_d(t_2 - t_1) \\ \frac{\text{dose} - D(t_1)}{\text{dose} - D(t_2)} &= e^{k_d(t_2 - t_1)} \\ \text{dose} - D(t_2) &= (\text{dose} - D(t_1)) \times e^{-k_d(t_2 - t_1)} \\ D(t_2) &= \text{dose} + (D(t_1) - \text{dose}) \times e^{-k_d(t_2 - t_1)}\end{aligned}$$